

Pest resistance – diseases

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to major diseases in Eastern Vidarbha Zone, India

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We screened 20 promising rice cultivars against major diseases prevailing in the Eastern Vidarbha Zone of Maharashtra State for 4 yr (1985-89). Promising high-yielding rices SKL-6, Sye 75, RP4-14, and SKL-6-1-23 were resistant or moderately resistant to blast, bacterial blight, and false smut (see table). ■

Resistance^c of 4 rice cultures to major diseases in Eastern Vidarbha zone, India, 1985-89.

Rice culture	Reaction			Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)
	Blast ^a	Bacterial blight ^a	False smut (%)		
SKL-6	1	1	0.2	115-120	4.0-5.0
Sye 75	2	1	0.4	130-135	4.5-5.5
RP4-14	1	2	0.3	125-130	5.0-5.5
SKL-6-1-23	2	1	0.3	135-140	4.5-5.0

^a Scored by the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Evaluation of resistance to blast (BI) in promising rice cultivars

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Screening for BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in different geographical zones is necessary because of different

physiogenic races and variation in environmental conditions.

We screened 20 promising rice cultivars under field conditions at Sindewahi, Eastern Vidarbha Zone, Maharashtra State.

Resistant cultivars were SKL-6, Pusa 33, and Sye 148-95 in the short-duration group, and RP4-14 and Jaya in the medium-duration group (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to BI in Eastern Vidarbha, Maharashtra, India.

Rice cultivar	Score ^a				Mean score
	1985-86	1986-87	1987-88	1988-89	
<i>Short duration</i>					
SKL-6	0	0	2	2	1
Nagpur 22	5	4	4	3	4
Tallahmsa	5	5	6	4	5
Ratna	1	3	2	2	2
IR36	2	2	2	1	1.7
Pusa 33	0	1	2	1	1
Sye 148-95	0	2	2	0	1
Tuljapur (check)	7	6	6	5	6
<i>Medium duration</i>					
Sye 75	2	2	2	2	2
RP4-14	1	1	2	0	1
Jaya	0	2	1	1	1
Sye 14-65-11	5	4	4	3	4
SKL 6-1-23	2	2	2	2	2
Sye 88-13-3-31	2	2	5	4	3.2
CR400-5 (check)	9	7	6	6	7
<i>Long duration</i>					
Pankaj	3	3	4	2	3
Jagannath	2	2	3	2	2.2
Chinoor	4	3	4	3	3.5
RTN68	3	2	2	2	2.2
Isha (check)	7	5	5	5	5.5

By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Evaluation of rice germplasm for resistance to grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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GSV is a serious constraint to rice production in the Kuttanad area of Kerala, India. Severe yellowing and stunting were observed in 1988 wet season (kharif) (May-Jun to Aug-Sep). All varieties grown were affected to some degree. Serological tests at Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, confirmed the presence of GSV.

We evaluated 362 rice accessions, including local varieties, under this heavy natural incidence. Each accession was planted in 2-m rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing and disease scored at panicle initiation.

Thirty accessions were moderately resistant to GSV; 15 were local and the remaining improved cultivars (see table). ■

Rice cultivars with moderate resistance to GSV. Kerala, India, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Damage score ^a (0-9)
Nampiaramban 10	3
Nampiaramban 133	3
Navara	3
Thonnooran	3
Pokkali 372	3
Nanthiyar vattom	3
Vasaramundan	3
Malakkaran	3
Chettiviruppu-Vettaackal	3
Anakkodan	3
Ptb 23 (Cheriya Aryan)	3
Athikira mundakan	3
Ponnaryan	3
Mundakan (D)	3
Kuruka	3
ARC6650	3
ARC 10550	3
Culture 74	4
IR42079	4
RP2547-988	4
K332	4
IR42076	4
RP1579-1367-68	4
KAU24-79-2	3
IET6315	4
IR24	4
KAU 1533-2	3
Intan	3
V643	3
IR42	4
TN1	9
IR50	9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.